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ABSTRACT BOOK

Posters

Diaphyseal femur fractures treated with intramedullary nail and quality of life after osteosynthesis

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SUMMARY

Introduction: The femur, the longest and strongest bone in the body, is not only protected by a large muscle mass but is also prone to fractures, especially high-energy fractures.

Methods: In this study, 72 patients with closed diaphyseal femoral fractures were included. The analysis period of the patients was conducted 24 months after surgery, comparing them with a non-operated control group of 20 healthy individuals. Both groups answered the SF-36 questionnaire, and by analyzing the answers we were able to assess functional abilities and quality of life.

Results: According to the categories of the SF-36 questionnaire, the average scores of the patients are as follows: in the category of physical functioning, the average score is 77.6, in the category of activity limitation due to physical health, the average score is 61.6, in the category of activity limitation due to emotional problems, the highest average score is 82.4, in the energy/fatigue category the lowest average score is 54, in the emotional well-being category the average score is 66.6, in the social function category the average score is good and is 81.6, in the pain category the average score is 71.6 and in the general health category the score is 64.3.

Conclusion: Overall, patients with intramedullary osteosynthesis of diaphyseal femur fractures have a statistically significantly lower overall quality of life than the healthy population.

Keywords: diaphyseal femoral fractures, intramedullary osteosynthesis, quality of life, SF-36 questionnaire